

Experimental determination of the transmission behavior of a pressure sensor array for torsobarography in posture analysis

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Abstract: In torsobarography, the dorsal pressure profile of a patient in supine position is recorded using a capacitive pressure sensor array with pliable underlying pad to extract parameters for posture analysis from this data. To assess the pressure mapping quality, this work introduces an initial approach to characterize the transmission behavior of the sensor array with underlying pad. Quality criteria and indices evaluating linearity, shift invariance, edge resolution, and ability to map height differences and convex or concave structures were developed. Experiments with test specimens were conducted to determine the transmission behavior dependent on compressive strength and thickness of the pad.

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I. Introduction

Early detection and treatment of postural deformities can prevent their progression [1]. For screening in this regard, torsobarography is an approach for the objective posture analysis of clothed subjects without ionizing radiation. The portable system contains a capacitive pressure sensor array with a pliable underlying pad. The subject is lying on the sensor, its measured dorsal pressure profile is analyzed and related to the anatomical back morphology. [2]

Reproducibility and precision of the pressure image vary with the properties of the underlying pad. Depending on its stiffness and thickness, the compression caused by the lying body changes. This influences the pressure image, particularly area and contour depth covered, maximum pressure, and edge sharpness (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Pressure images of human dorsal torso morphology (same subject). Pressure sensor array with polyurethane foam pad (thickness $d = 40$ mm). Left soft pad (compressive strength $R_s = 20$ hPa), right harder ($R_s = 60$ hPa). Using the harder pad, the lumbar area is mapped insufficiently, but prominent structures are clearly located.

For systems combining pressure sensor array and mattresses or seat cushions, sensor and mattress are

commonly considered as one unit [3] or systems with e. g. two different cushions are compared [4]. Currently, neither a method of assessment nor objective quality criteria are established to describe the transmission behavior of the system dependent on material properties of the pad and no systematic investigations with different materials were conducted. Theoretical modeling of the system is challenging due to a lack of fundamental knowledge about its behavior and therefore unknown model parameters.

Goal of this work is the fundamental objective characterization of the transmission behavior of a system consisting of a capacitive pressure sensor array and a pliable underlying polyurethane foam pad depending on the compressive strength R_s and thickness d of the used material.

II. Material and methods

For this purpose, quality criteria and parameters were developed (Table 1). Linearity and displacement invariance are fundamental characteristics of the abstract system transferring the back morphology at the input to a pressure image at the output. For torsobarography, the precise resolution of edges and prominent points, e. g. shoulder blades, and the distinguishable mapping of convex or concave structures, e. g. the concave canal in the spinal range, and height differences, e. g. the rib hump, is important to ensure sufficient imaging and therefore more reliable posture classification quality.

A test series with polyurethane foam pads ($d = 20$ mm to 140 mm, $R_s = 20$ hPa to 60 hPa) was conducted using a capacitive pressure sensor array (LX100:100.160.05, XSENSOR Technology Corporation, Calgary, AB, Canada, 100 x 160 sensors, measurement area 50.8 cm x 81.2 cm, calibrated pressure range 0.07 N/cm² to 2.7 N/cm², accuracy ± 5 %) and rigid test specimens (circular plates with diameter 100 mm to 150 mm, or,

regarding height differences and convex or concave structures, specimens with a sinusoidal height downside profile, amplitude 1 mm to 5 mm, distance between maxima 20 mm to 80 mm, three to five maxima) loaded with weights from 1250 g to 6250 g. Conducting each measurement with full factorial experimental design for multiple combinations of material thickness and compressive strength, with different loads and test specimens iterated with repositioning of the specimen, in total, 1800 measurements were recorded.

Table 1: Developed quality criteria and parameters to characterize the transmission behavior of a pressure sensor array with pliable underlying pad

Quality criterion	Parameter
Linearity	Coefficient of determination R^2 for linear regression of the average pressure values in the central test specimen area
Displacement invariance	Statistical results regarding frequency distribution of measured values within discrete pressure levels at the different locations Coefficient of variation of the mean pressure values across different measurement locations
Edge resolution	Distance from object edge where still pressure recognized (above the lower calibration limit)
Mapping of height differences and convex or concave structures	Relative mean pressure difference of local extrema for different amplitudes with same pad Distance between prominent points where still clearly localizable Ratio of area mapped with pressure values recognizable above the lower calibration limit

III. Results and discussion

In Figure 2, an overview of the expression of the quality criteria with different pad material properties is provided.

Figure 2: Expression of the quality criteria for a system of pressure sensor array and underlying polyurethane foam pad (thickness $d = 40$ mm, different compressive strengths). The further a parameter entry is distanced from the center, the better pronounced is the criterion.

Regarding linearity, the coefficient of determination for linear regression of the average pressure values in the central specimen area ranged from $R^2 = 0.625$ ($d = 80$ mm, $R_s = 20$ hPa) to $R^2 = 0.996$ ($d = 20$ mm, $R_s = 60$ hPa) with no distinct cohesion of material parameters and regression. The higher R_s , the higher was the slope a of the regression line from $a = 0.158$ ($d = 140$ mm, $R_s = 20$ hPa) to $a = 0.804$ ($d = 20$ mm, $R_s = 60$ hPa). Especially at the object edges, the system showed nonlinearity.

Evaluating the frequency distribution deviations of the discretized pressure values between the individual

measurement locations, the system showed no shift invariance. Nevertheless, regarding the average of the pressure values at the different locations, the coefficient of variation was $< 6\%$ between the used material properties, principally indicating a similarity of the pressure images.

Concerning edge resolution, the lower R_s and the greater the load on the specimen, the greater was the width b of the approximated circular area around the object edge, where the measured pressure was still above the lower calibration limit. For $R_s = 60$ hPa, a maximum width $b = 0.5$ cm and for $R_s = 20$ hPa, $b = 2.3$ cm was calculated.

The higher R_s , the larger was the number of distinctive discriminable height differences (mean pressure difference of local extrema for different amplitudes $> 10\%$) and the distance between clearly localizable prominent points. The lower R_s and tendentially the thicker the pad, the bigger was the ratio of the specimen area, which was recorded within the calibration range. In average, it ranged from 34.6% ($R_s = 60$ hPa) to 75.9% ($R_s = 20$ hPa).

Therefore, softer materials allowed more detailed structure mapping in the calibrated pressure range, harder materials provided a more precise differentiation of amplitude differences, localization of edges and prominent points.

IV. Conclusions

A first approach of objective quality criteria and parameters was developed to characterize the transmission behavior of a capacitive pressure sensor array with a pliable underlying polyurethane foam pad depending on its mechanical properties. These consider linearity, displacement invariance, resolution of object edges and ability to map height differences and convex or concave structures, thus enabling an objective comparison of different systems. Based on 1800 measurements with rigid test specimens, this work provides extensive data sets for the mapping of structures by the system. In addition, it enables findings on the system behavior with representative compression hardnesses and thicknesses of the pad as well as conclusions on further correlations with these properties. The abstracted methods, quality criteria and parameters developed can be transferred to other systems.

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